

Vertex-Mean Graphs

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Abstract: Let $k \geq 0$ be an integer. A *Smarandachely vertex-mean k -labeling* of a (p, q) graph $G = (V, E)$ is such an injection $f : E \rightarrow \{0, 1, 2, \dots, q_* + k\}$, $q_* = \max(p, q)$ such that the function $f^V : V \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ defined by the rule $f^V(v) = \text{Round}\left(\frac{\sum_{e \in E_v} f(e)}{d(v)}\right) - k$ satisfies the property that $f^V(V) = \{f^V(u) : u \in V\} = \{1, 2, \dots, p\}$, where E_v denotes the set of edges in G that are incident at v , \mathbb{N} denotes the set of all natural numbers and *Round* is the *nearest integer function*. A graph that has a Smarandachely vertex-mean k -labeling is called *Smarandachely k vertex-mean graph* or *Smarandachely k V -mean graph*. Particularly, if $k = 0$, such a Smarandachely vertex-mean 0-labeling and Smarandachely 0 vertex-mean graph or Smarandachely 0 V -mean graph is called a *vertex-mean labeling* and a *vertex-mean graph* or *V -mean graph*, respectively. In this paper, we obtain necessary conditions for a graph to be V -mean and study V -mean behaviour of certain classes of graphs.

Key Words: Smarandachely vertex-mean k -labeling, vertex-mean labeling, edge labeling, Smarandachely k vertex-mean graph, vertex-mean graph.

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§1. Introduction

A vertex labeling of a graph G is an assignment f of labels to the vertices of G that induces a label for each edge xy depending on the vertex labels. An *edge labeling* of a graph G is an assignment f of labels to the edges of G that induces a label for each vertex v depending on the labels of the edges incident on it. Vertex labelings such as *graceful labeling*, *harmonious labeling* and *mean labeling* and edge labelings such as *edge-magic labeling*, *(a, d) -anti magic labeling* and *vertex-graceful labeling* are some of the interesting labelings found in the dynamic survey of graph labeling by Gallian [3]. In fact B. D. Acharya [2] has introduced *vertex-graceful graphs*, as an edge-analogue of *graceful graphs*. Observe that, in a variety of practical problems, the arithmetic mean, X , of a finite set of real numbers $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ serves as a

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better estimate for it, in the sense that $\sum(x_i - X)$ is zero and $\sum(x_i - X)^2$ is the minimum. If it is required to use a single integer in the place of X then $Round(X)$ does this best, in the sense that $\sum(x_i - Round(X))$ and $\sum(x_i - Round(X))^2$ are minimum, where $Round(Y)$, nearest integer function of a real number, gives the integer closest to Y ; to avoid ambiguity, it is defined to be the nearest even integer in the case of half integers. This motivates us to define the edge-analogue of the *mean labeling* introduced by R. Ponraj [1]. A *mean labeling* f is an injection from V to the set $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, q\}$ such that the set of edge labels defined by the rule $Round(\frac{f(u) + f(v)}{2})$ for each edge uv is $\{1, 2, \dots, q\}$. For all terminology and notations in graph theory, we refer the reader to the text book by D. B. West [4]. All graphs considered in the paper are finite and simple.

Fig.1 Some V -mean graphs

Fig.2

Definition 1.1 Let $k \geq 0$ be an integer. A Smarandachely vertex-mean k -labeling of a (p, q) graph $G = (V, E)$ is such an injection $f : E \rightarrow \{0, 1, 2, \dots, q_* + k\}$, $q_* = \max(p, q)$ such that the function $f^V : V \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ defined by the rule $f^V(v) = \text{Round}\left(\frac{\sum_{e \in E_v} f(e)}{d(v)}\right) - k$ satisfies the property that $f^V(V) = \{f^V(u) : u \in V\} = \{1, 2, \dots, p\}$, where E_v denotes the set of edges in G that are incident at v , \mathbb{N} denotes the set of all natural numbers and Round is the nearest integer function. A graph that has a Smarandachely vertex-mean k -labeling is called Smarandachely k vertex-mean graph or Smarandachely k V -mean graph. Particularly, if $k = 0$, such a Smarandachely vertex-mean 0 -labeling and Smarandachely 0 vertex-mean graph or Smarandachely 0 V -mean graph is called a vertex-mean labeling and a vertex-mean graph or V -mean graph, respectively.

Henceforth we call vertex-mean as V -mean. To initiate the investigation, we obtain necessary conditions for a graph to be a V -mean graph and we present some results on this new notion in this paper. In Fig.1 we give some V -mean graphs and in Fig.2, we give some non V -mean graphs.

§2. Necessary Conditions

Following observations are obvious from Definition 1.1.

Observation 2.1 If G is a V -mean graph then no V -mean labeling assigns 0 to a pendant edge.

Observation 2.2 The graph K_2 and disjoint union of K_2 are not V -mean graphs, as any number assigned to an edge uv leads to assignment of same number to each of u and v . Thus every component of a V -mean graph has at least two edges.

Observation 2.3 The minimum degree of any V -mean graph is less than or equal to three ie, $\delta \leq 3$ as $\text{Round}(0 + 1 + 2 + 3)$ is 2 . Thus graphs that contain a r -regular graph, where $r \geq 4$ as spanning sub graph are not V -mean graphs and any 3 -edge-connected V -mean graph has a vertex of degree three.

Observation 2.4 If f is a V -mean labeling of a graph G then either (1) or (2) of the following is satisfied according as the induced vertex label $f^V(v)$ is obtained by rounding up or rounding down.

$$f^V(v)d(v) \leq \sum_{e \in E_v} f(e) + \frac{1}{2}d(v), \quad (1)$$

$$f^V(v)d(v) \geq \sum_{e \in E_v} f(e) - \frac{1}{2}d(v). \quad (2)$$

Theorem 2.5 If G is a V -mean graph then the vertices of G can be arranged as v_1, v_2, \dots, v_p such that $q^2 - 2q \leq \sum_1^p kd(v_k) \leq 2qq_* - q^2 + 2q$.

Proof Let f be a V -mean labeling of a graph G . Let us denote the vertex that has the induced vertex label k , $1 \leq k \leq p$ as v_k . Observe that, $\sum_{v \in V} f^V(v)d(v)$ attains it maximum/minimum when each induced vertex label is obtained by rounding up/down and the first

q largest/smallest values of the set $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, q_*\}$ are assigned as edge labels by f . This with Observation 2.4 completes the proof. \square

Corollary 2.6 Any 3-regular graph of order $2m$, $m \geq 4$ is not a V -mean graph.

Corollary 2.7 The ladder $L_n = P_n \times P_2$, $n \geq 7$ is not a V -mean graph.

A V -mean labeling of ladders L_3 and L_4 are shown in Figure 1.

§3. Classes of V -Mean Graphs

Theorem 3.1 If $n \geq 3$ then the path P_n is V -mean graph.

Proof Let $\{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_{n-1}\}$ be the edge set of P_n such that $e_i = v_i v_{i+1}$. We define $f : E \rightarrow \{0, 1, 2, \dots, q_* = p\}$ as follows:

$$f(e_i) = \begin{cases} i, & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq p-2, \\ i+1, & \text{if } i = p-1. \end{cases}$$

It can be easily verified that f is a V -mean labeling. \square

A V -mean labeling of P_{10} is shown in Fig.3.

Fig.3

Theorem 3.2 If $n \geq 3$ then the cycle C_n is V -mean graph.

Proof Let $\{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}$ be the edge set of C_n such that $e_i = v_i v_{i+1}$, $1 \leq i \leq n-1$, $e_n = v_n v_1$. Let $\zeta = \lceil \frac{n}{2} \rceil - 1$. The edges of C_n are labeled as follows: The numbers $0, 1, 2, \dots, n$ except ζ are arranged in an increasing sequence $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n$ and α_k is assigned to e_k . Clearly the edges of C_n receive distinct labels and the vertex labels induced are $1, 2, \dots, n$. Thus C_n is V -mean graph. \square

The corona $G_1 \odot G_2$ of two graphs $G_1(p_1, q_1)$ and $G_2(p_2, q_2)$ is defined as the graph obtained by taking one copy of G_1 and p_1 copies of G_2 and then joining the i^{th} vertex of G_1 to all the vertices in the i^{th} copy of G_2 . The graph $C_n \odot K_1$ is called a *crown*.

Theorem 3.3 The corona $P_n \odot K_m^C$, where $n \geq 2$ and $m \geq 1$ is V -mean graph.

Proof Let the vertex set and the edge set of $G = P_n \odot K_m^C$ be as follows:

$$V(G) = \{u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{u_{ij} : 1 \leq i \leq n \text{ and } 1 \leq j \leq m\},$$

$$E(G) = A \cup B,$$

where $A = \{e_i = u_i u_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n - 1\}$ and $B = \{e_{ij} = u_i u_{ij} : 1 \leq i \leq n \text{ and } 1 \leq j \leq m\}$. We observe that G has order $(m + 1)n$ and size $(m + 1)n - 1$. The edges of G are labeled in three steps as follows :

Step 1. The edges e_1 and $e_{1j}, 1 \leq j \leq m$ are assigned distinct integers from 1 to $(m + 1)$ in such a way that e_1 receives the number $Round(\frac{\sum_{j=1}^{m+1} j}{m + 1})$.

Step 2. For each $i, 2 \leq i \leq n - 1$, the edges e_i and $e_{ij}, 1 \leq j \leq m$ are assigned distinct integers from $(m + 1)(i - 1) + 1$ to $(m + 1)i$ in such a way that e_i receives the number

$$Round(\frac{f(e_{i-1}) + \sum_{j=1}^{m+1} (m + 1)(i - 1) + j}{m + 2}).$$

Step 3. The edges $e_{nj}, 1 \leq j \leq m$ are assigned distinct integers from $(m + 1)(n - 1) + 1$ to $(m + 1)n$ in such a way that non of these edges receive the number

$$Round(\frac{f(e_{n-1}) + \sum_{j=1}^{m+1} (m + 1)(n - 1) + j}{m + 2}).$$

Then the edges of G receive distinct labels and the vertex labels induced are $1, 2, \dots, (m + 1)n$. Thus G is V -mean graph.

Fig.4 displays a V -mean labeling of $P_5 \odot K_4^C$.

Fig.4 A V -mean labeling of $P_5 \odot K_4^C$

Theorem 3.4 *The star graph $K_{1,n}$ is V -mean graph if and only if $n \cong 0(mod2)$.*

Proof Necessity: Suppose $G = K_{1,n}, n = 2m + 1$ for some $m \geq 1$ is V -mean and let f be a V -mean labeling of G . As no V -mean labeling assigns zero to a pendant edge, f assigns $2m + 1$ distinct numbers from the set $\{1, 2, \dots, 2m + 2\}$ to the edges of G . Observe that, whatever be the labels assigned to the edges of G , label induced on the central vertex of G will be either $m + 1$ or $m + 2$. In both cases two vertex labels induced on G will be identical. This contradiction proves *necessity*.

Sufficiency: Let $G = K_{1,n}, n = 2m$ for some $m \geq 1$. Then assignment of $2m$ distinct numbers except $m + 1$ from the set $\{1, 2, \dots, 2m + 1\}$ gives the desired V -mean labeling of G .□

Theorem 3.5 *The crown $C_n \odot K_1$ is V -mean graph.*

Proof Let the vertex set and the edge set of $G = C_n \odot K_1$ be as follows: $V(G) = \{u_i, v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$, $E(G) = A \cup B$ where $A = \{e_i = u_i u_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{e_n = u_n u_1\}$ and $B = \{e'_i = u_i v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$. Observe that G has order and size both equal to $2n$. For $3 \leq n \leq 5$, V -mean labeling of G are shown in Fig.5. For $n \geq 6$, define $f : E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2n\}$ as follows:

Case 1 $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$.

$$f(e_i) = \begin{cases} 2i - 2 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{3} - 1, \\ 2i & \text{if } i = \frac{n}{3}, \\ 2i - 1 & \text{if } \frac{n}{3} + 1 \leq i \leq n, \end{cases}$$

$$f(e'_i) = \begin{cases} 2i - 1 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{3}, \\ 2i & \text{if } \frac{n}{3} + 1 \leq i \leq n. \end{cases}$$

Case 2 $n \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$.

$$f(e_i) = \begin{cases} 2i - 2 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{3} \rfloor, \\ 2i - 1 & \text{if } \lfloor \frac{n}{3} \rfloor + 1 \leq i \leq n, \end{cases}$$

$$f(e'_i) = \begin{cases} 2i - 1 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{3} \rfloor, \\ 2i & \text{if } \lfloor \frac{n}{3} \rfloor + 1 \leq i \leq n. \end{cases}$$

It can be easily verified that f is a V -mean labeling of G . □

A V -mean labeling of some crowns are shown in Fig.5.

Fig.5 V -mean labeling of crowns for $n = 3, 4, 5$

Problem 3.6 Determine new classes of trees and unicyclic graphs which are V -mean graphs.

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